

New studies on bisphenol A do not challenge earlier risk assessment

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Two new studies from the USA relaunched discussions this week about the substance, bisphenol A. The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) has examined whether the studies provide findings which make it necessary to change health risk assessment. Bearing in mind the data from the two studies, the Institute does not see any reason to change the prior risk assessment of bisphenol A. If the tolerable daily intake (TDI) of 0.05 milligram bisphenol A per kilogram bodyweight established by the European Food Safety Authority in 2007 is complied with, there is no health risk for consumers. The two studies do, however, reveal that there is a need for further research on the effects of bisphenol A on the human organism. New research results are continuously examined by BfR and included in risk assessment.

The full version of this BfR Information is available in German on http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/216/neue_studien_zu_bisphenol_a_stellen_die_bisherige_risikobewertung_nicht_in_frage.pdf